

Research Article

Innovation For Lab Coat

Nur Hani Insyirah Norman¹, and Siti Amira Othman^{2,*}

¹ Faculty of Applied Sciences and Technology, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, 84600, Pagoh, Johor.

² Faculty of Applied Sciences and Technology, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, 84600, Pagoh, Johor.

* Correspondence: sitiamira@uthm.edu.my.

Abstract: Laboratory coats are a crucial equipment of worker protection in both laboratory and clinical or patient care areas. Lab coats must be worn whenever working in the laboratory or clinical areas to protect against accidental spill or contact. The important of lab coat are to ensure protection of skin and personal clothing from incidental or unpredictable contact and small splashes during handle dangerous substances. It also helps to prevent the spread of contamination outside the lab such a virus. Lab coat act as a removable barrier in the event of an incident involving a spill or splash of hazardous substances. We can assume that lab coat also acts as shield to protect ourselves from further serious accident. Lab coat innovation has been widespread to advance gradually with technology and current situations which more challenging to face hazard exposure and others problem. We knew there are many scientists had done some innovation of lab coat such as smart fabrics which already implemented in specific industries, but it is not easy as we can see. The reasons are how we attach the other materials which electronic like a sensor in a lab coat without make it uncomfortable to it users. It is also become problems when the materials or substances that we want to use is dangerous towards human but at the same time crucial to make innovation at the lab coat to reduce the hazards exposure.

Keywords: Lab coat; innovation; PPE.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

PPE is short form from the Personal Protective Equipment which has been worn to minimize exposure toward hazards, reduce incident and accident probability to happen in workplace that will cause serious injuries and illnesses to employee or employer. Injuries and illnesses may occur from proximity hazards such as radiological, chemical, mechanical, electrical, physical, noise, dust, and heavy machinery or other danger in workplace. Personal protective equipment may consist equipment such as leather gloves, nitrile gloves, lab coat, welding coat, chemical resistant boots, welding goggles, laser protection goggles, ear muffs, ear plugs, respirator, safety vests, steel toe booth, coveralls, hard hat or dielectric boots.

Personal protective equipment should be kept in a clean and reliable fashion in the same time properties the safety. PPE should be comfortable for anyone that will be use it. However, when the personal protective equipment does not fit properly, there will be the difference between being safely covered and hazards exposure. Because of that, employers must provide personal protective equipment to their workers and ensure its proper use. Employers are also required to train each worker to know the use of personal protective equipment in term of when it is necessary to use PPE, the properly ways

to put it on, adjust, wear and take it off, the limitations of the equipment Proper care, maintenance, useful life, and disposal of the equipment.

The purpose of PPE is to protect the health and safety of workers by reducing their exposure toward hazards and to minimize the occupational illnesses and injuries. The proper use of PPE is important to make sure the safety and health of workers in various industries, including construction, healthcare, and manufacturing. Individual's injuries and illnesses can be significantly reduced by wearing appropriate and suitable protective gear. Therefore, PPE can promote safer and more productive work environment. Additionally, stick to PPE guidelines will helps organizations comply with safety regulations and standards. It is also ultimately contributing to overall operational effectiveness and employee well-being.

According to the hierarchy of controls by the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH), PPE is recommended to be the final level of defence to prevent occupational injuries, illnesses and fatalities. However, some businesses had combined it with other control measures to ensure a safe and healthy environment for their workers in full potential. The advantages of PPE are preventing unnecessary or unpredictable injury in the workplace, protect employees from numerous chemical exposures, prevent the spread of germs and infectious diseases such as COVID-19 and help businesses comply with regulatory requirements. For those benefits of PPE, The Personal Protective Equipment at Work Regulations 1992 has been extended to limb workers to improve employee productivity and efficiency.

According to Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) guidelines, a laboratory coat or equivalent protection is necessary when work with or near hazardous chemicals, unsealed radioactive materials and biological agents at Biosafety Level 2 (BL2). For an example, a flame-resistant lab coat is essential when handling pyrophoric substances or hazards materials outside of a glove box.

2. CURRENT INNOVATION

This is a current or commonly lab coat that worker usually wear during in the laboratory to handle chemical or biological substance. There is simple that all people in the world use this lab coat even student when do experiment. However, there are no advanced or specific items that can handle hazards or can sent warning to users. The criteria in lab coat had an additional layer of protection for skin, protects area not already covered by clothing, materials 100% cotton in labs, cover the wearer to the knees, long sleeves,2 patch pockets at bottom part,1 chest pocket at left side and snap button opening for easy access.

Lab coats should have these following characteristics to provide the best protection:

1. Sleeves – Knitted types are preferable or gathered sleeves to reduce wrist exposure and avoid sample contamination.
2. Front Closure – Design for fast removal in event of a splash or snaps extending to top of lab coat.
3. Material – Based on types of hazard exposure. Polyester or cotton blend for general chemical and biological.
4. Colour – related to material for easy identification. white for poly/cotton and blue for flame resistant materials.

3. FINDINGS: INNOVATION OF LAB COAT

3.1 *Ultraviolet (UV) and radiation exposure sensors*

The concept of these sensors is the sensor can measure the amount of UV or radiation that expose to workers during lab work make it more safety by providing real-time alerts if exposure radiation levels exceed safety limits. This can protect workers from effect of radiation to not exposure by radiation in a long period.

This sensor could work by use a tiny dosimeter which the devices that can measure radiation this device can be inserted into the coat because it size. It is also can help with tracking cumulative radiation exposure. Photodiode sensors could detect UV light and give the sign to user when it reaches limit levels. The data could be displayed and sent to a connected device such as phone, tablet or computer. This innovation can be convenient to lab workers as they do not fully to depend on ultraviolet (UV) and radiation sensors in laboratory because they have this sensor in their lab coats. The high technology is needed as ensuring the sensors are small, lightweight, not interfere with the functionality of the coat, making them affordable and scalable for widespread use in the laboratory and industrial.

3.2 *Chemical colourless spill dyes*

The concept is chemical-reactive dyes will integrate into the lab coat fabric. The function is to detect and identify hazardous chemical spills like higher concentration colourless acids. This can avoid wearer to prevent the colourless chemical to make a contact with skin. The chemical colourless spill dyes will add at several part only such as wrist or arm part that usually expose to colourless chemical like hydrochloric acid (HCL) and sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄).

This innovation could work with embedded the lab coat fabric with chemical-reactive dyes that change colour when they encounter with a colourless of chemicals such as acid. Bromothymol blue is reacted with colourless acid, the pH will fall below pH6 make the colour of bromothymol blue change from blue to yellow. This reversible reaction can be used to monitor concentration of acid or to detect the presence of acidic conditions. The Bromothymol blues is generally considered as safe when we used in small amounts for laboratory purposes like pH detected.

However, the Bromothymol blues is very sensitive to exchange environment make it react quickly when react with the acid and alkaline. It is also not commonly used as a dye because Bromothymol blues is use as a pH indicator. As my concern, the blue colour will fade with time or after exposure to neutral conditions since it is not designed as dyes. We can overcome this problem as rapid in technology development, this problem may be solved by combine the Bromothymol blues with a fabrics dyes make it more suitable for be a chemical colourless spill dyes that crucial to lab coat in the future.

3.3 *Health sensor*

The concept of health sensor is to measure the heartbeat rate, pulse rate and blood pressure to check whether the workers are in a good condition or not during do the lab work. The health sensor will add at wrist or heart part in micro sensor size that suitable to monitor workers health and comfortable to use the lab coat. The health sensor in the small size modification from health sensor that usually attached at smartwatches. The function of health sensor changes by follow the lab coat requirements and world demand.

The health sensor can be work by use micro pulse sensor that place at wrist or heart part at the lab coat. It is also can detect abnormally or normally heartbeat, pulse rate and blood pressure. The data will transfer to a connected device, or the micro pulse sensor will vibrate as a warning sign.

Micro health sensor can give a signal to workers by detect heart complication during do the lab work. This can be very helpful to monitor and take care of employee's welfare before any unpredictable event occurs such as heart attack that led to death.

4. DISCUSSION: APPLICATION OF LAB COAT

The innovation in application of lab coat is crucial to develop together with technology to overcome current and future problems that human will face. The ideas innovation above basically can use in chemical laboratories or suitable industries. It is also can be using by worker in industrial which deal with dangerous chemical and can use by any laboratory's assistant. In occupational safety, these innovations are identifying ergonomic risks in the workplace, monitoring worker fatigue at the same time preventing accidents.

First, the application of chemical colourless spill dyes in lab coat will help lab workers in dealing with hazardous chemicals. When bromothymol blue is added to colourless acid, the pH of the solution drops falls below about pH 6. So, the colour of bromothymol blue will shift from blue to yellow. This reversible reaction can be used to monitor acid strength or to detect the presence of acidic conditions in a solution. The colour change of dyes would immediately let the lab workers know that they are probably exposed to harmful colourless chemical like acid even the colourless chemical in a small amount.

Second, the application of ultraviolet (UV) and radiation exposure sensors are convenient in labs where lab workers are usually exposed to UV sterilization or radiation sources in specific industries or lab. The sensor will collect data about radiation exposure and transfer the data into connected devices. It is also can monitor the ultraviolet and radiation to always in safety limit by process the data based on unharmed and harmful radiation.

Third, the application of health sensor will help the lab workers will know about their inner issues such as heart complications to avoid high chance incident or accident to occurs such as heart attack. This also can reduce the sudden death among the workers and help administration to prove that all workers are fully prepare with complete PPE to ensure their safety in laboratories or industrials. Potential applications of health sensor in healthcare to monitor patient rehabilitation progress and detect early signs of heart disease.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, these innovation ideas of lab coat reveal the potential and functionality of lab coats. Through a comprehensive analysis of current lab coat, we can create future lab coat design performance based on these innovations. The innovation can enhance protection to the worker during working hours at the laboratory or industrial area. The sensors could detect potential hazards and trigger protective mechanisms, such as health sensor and UV and radiation sensor to safeguard the wearer. Second, efficiency can increase as the innovation feature such as UV and radiation sensor and health sensor have automatics systems to send the data straight to the connected devices to reduce time spent on non-essential tasks. Data collection and analysis capabilities could enable real-time monitoring of environmental and wearer conditions and performance, leading to improved decision-making and low risk.

The lab coat innovations present a great performance for enhancing safety, efficiency, and data-driven insights in laboratory settings. Future research should focus on developing advanced sensor technologies to realize the full potential of this innovative approach. The innovation must advance gradually with technology because in the future there are increase of cases with different difficulty level. Lab coat as a PPE also need to make an innovation to match with current situations and problem as the more expansion in technology, there are more problems will exist. The innovation may be impossible, but it is not possible to create as the world demand for maximum safety for the workers. The reason is that science and technology can help the innovation which these two things can make the change in innovation in PPE. In short, the innovation purpose is for the safety of workers and reduce the death in workplace to manage the workers welfare to create an efficient and satisfied workforce.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to thank the Faculty of Applied Sciences and Technology, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia for facilities provided that make the research possible.

References

- Bertalan, Mesko. (May 2, 2024), *finally a good wearable blood pressure monitor: Aktiia bracelet review*. Retrieved from <https://medicalfuturist.com/category/health-sensors-trackers/>
- Guren Matsumura, et al. (October 21, 2024). Real-time personal healthcare data analysis using edge computing for multimodal wearable sensors. *Device*.
- Mark Saner. (August 01, 2017). *The do's and don'ts of lab coats*. Retrieved from <https://ohsonline.com/Articles/2017/08/01/Dos-and-Donts-of-Lab-Coats.aspx>
- Massachusetts Institute of Technology, (Environment, Health & Safety Office). Retrieved from <https://labcoats.mit.edu/>
- Occupational Safety and Health Committee, (2016). Retrieved from <https://ors.od.nih.gov/sr/dohs/Documents/laboratory-coat-selection-guidance.pdf>
- Renkee, (April 18,2024). *Know more about the UV sensor*. Retrieved from <https://www.renkeer.com/what-is-uv-sensor/>
- Ritika Singla (n.d.). *What is bromothymol blue?* Retrieved from <https://www.vedantu.com/chemistry/bromothymol-blue>